

STUDENTS' ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AND PRACTICES: BASIS FOR REDEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL SOLIDWASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AT SCHOOL LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

Environmental problems persist in schools despite numerous efforts to implement a policy on waste management. The study aimed to determine the respondents' level of perception of environmental awareness in terms of Environmental Concepts / State of Environment, Environmental Issues/Problems, Formulating alternative solutions, Taking action in solving problems, and Possessing a high degree of commitment and advocacy, the perceived level of environmental practices in terms of Minimisation, Segregation at Source, Reducing, Reuse, Recycle, and Composting, and the level of perception of the delivery of ecological solid waste management systems at the school level as to Integration to the school curriculum and Inclusion in the School Improvement Plan, as the basis for the redevelopment of ecological solid waste management system at school level. Using a descriptive research design, it involved 109 respondents from grade levels 4, 5, and 6 enrolled at San Gabriel Elementary School, San Pablo City, Laguna for the School Year 2020-2021. Survey-questionnaires were used to measure Environmental Awareness, Environmental Practices, and level of perception of the delivery of ecological solid waste management systems at the school level. Results revealed that in terms of Environmental Awareness, the respondents are "Moderately Aware". It was also revealed that the respondents "Moderately Practiced" Environmental Practices. The respondents' level of perception of the delivery of ecological solid waste management system at the school level was interpreted as "Moderately Aware". It was also observed that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' level of perception of environmental awareness and the respondents' level of perception of the delivery of ecological solid waste management systems at the school level. A significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of environmental practices and the level of the respondents' perception of the delivery of ecological solid waste management systems at the school level was likewise noted.

Keywords: Science and Technology, Environmental Science, Environmental Awareness, Environmental Practices, Ecological Solid Waste Management System at School Level, Descriptive Correlational Study, Republic of the Philippines, Asia